

The Effects of some Heteropoly Complexes of Transition Metals (Sodium Molybdoaluminate and Sodium Vanadoaluminate) on the Process of Germination in some Plants

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The effects of heavy metals and their role in various plant metabolic activities are well documented^{1,2} and established. Perusal of literature shows that these substances have profound effect on various cellular systems, at organisational level and regulatory at molecular levels^{3,4}. In this communication the effects of heteropoly complexes of transition metals like vanadium and molybdenum on the process of germination and rate of radicle growth in three plants, namely *Allium cepa*, *Vicia faba* and *Lens culinaris* are highlighted.

Results and Discussion

The results indicate that sodium molybdoaluminate exhibited stimulatory effects on the percentage and rate of germination in the concentration range 1–10 ppm in all plants under consideration. The concentration above 15 and 20 ppm were detrimental and showed complete inhibition at 25 ppm. Un-like this, the effects of sodium vanadoaluminate on the percentage and rate of germination was antagonising as there was lesser percentage of germination at the concentration of 1 ppm in respect to the controls. Such difference in the percentage of germination is attributable to pre-ferential choice between molecules in these plants. The stimulatory effects of sodium molybdoaluminate might be

attributed to the fact that low concentration of these substances might affect enzyme-mediated cellular processes which depend on the optimal values of numerous factors, leading to the enhancement of the process. On the other hand, the negative and antagonistic affects of sodium vanadoaluminate in respect to germination and growth were due to inhibitory or toxic actions of the substance. The stimulatory affects of molybdenum in low concentration have been reported in many crops and horticultural plants³. Whereas, inhibitory, antagonistic and toxic effects of many heavy and transition metals in various plant materials are experimentally well established⁴. The above findings are in consonance with the findings of the earlier workers^{1,3,4}.

Experimental

Dry and dormant seeds of *V. faba* and *L. culinaris* and bulbs of *A. cepa* procured from the local sources were used as experimental plant materials for the studies of germination percentage and the growth rate of roots. The heteropoly complexes of vanadium(v) and molybdenum(vi) belonging to d^0 transition metals, contain water in the interstics and peripheral regions of the crystals, acting as water of crystallisation and/or as water of constitution². Aqueous solutions

of sodium molybdoaluminate and sodium vanadate in the concentration of 1, 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 ppm were prepared in double-distilled water. The seeds and the bulbs were soaked in these solutions for 2–3 h, then washed with water and placed in germination chamber along with the controls, maintained at $23 \pm 2^\circ$ with 76% relative humidity. Each treatment consisted of at least 20 seeds and bulbs and 10 replicates were taken into consideration for both the controls and the treated seeds and bulbs. The percentage of germination was accounted right from the time of the emergence of the radicle from the seed coat and stock. The rate of germination was ascertained by directly measuring the length of the radicle between

8 and 10 a.m. every day upto 7 days of observations.

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